

Comparison of state-of-the-art regionalization techniques coupled with SWAT for predicting streamflow in ungauged watersheds in Eastern India

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Abstract

In India, it is observed that numerous catchments lack streamflow measurements that affects the scope for studies on the hydrological processes and extreme events, as well as watershed management. The proposed study focuses on streamflow estimation in ungauged basin in Eastern India by applying regionalization techniques coupled with the popular Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) hydrological model. As first step, performance of the different state-of-the-art regionalization techniques, namely, physical similarity (PS) and inverse distance weighting (IDW) based methods are improved by prior classification of hydrologically similar watersheds in the Eastern India into homogeneous clusters. In this study, a pseudo-ungauged watershed in the Subarnarekha-Brahmani-Baitarani River Basin region is chosen to investigate the performance of the different regionalization approaches, after transferring the parameters from most similar watersheds to the pseudo-ungauged watershed. A combination of different classification algorithms and regionalization methods on model parameters are tested and compared on the selected study gauged watersheds. The two regionalization methods are applied on the clusters obtained after dimensionality reduction approaches based on principal components analysis (PCA) and Isomap (for non-linear dimensionality reduction) followed by simple K-means clustering classification. The attributes involved in the classification are extracted from watershed characteristics, hydro-meteorological data and calibrated SWAT model parameters. The Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2) values of streamflow in pseudo-ungauged basin are respectively 0.80 and 0.76 when the PCA is combined with IDW, 0.73 and 0.72 when Isomap is combined with IDW, and 0.73 and 0.71 with the physical similarity-based approach. Based on the results of this study, the combination of PCA and IDW is recommended. Further, by including a larger number of watersheds and soil characteristics in the study, the efficiency of the regionalization can be improved.

Keywords: Regionalization; Principal component analysis; Isomap; Soil and Water Assessment Tool; Inverse Distance Weighting; Physical Similarity; K-means Clustering

1 Introduction

Watershed management requires the availability of continuous hydro-meteorological observations and water balance simulation is difficult if streamflow observations are lacking. This limits the scope for climate and land use/ cover change impact assessment and extreme event studies over ungauged catchments. In this context, the method of regionalization of hydrological models could be useful for these regions. Regionalization is the process of

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transferring hydrological model parameters from adjacent gauged catchments to targeted ungauged catchments. This technique has been widely used to develop hydrological datasets for ungauged catchments. Since 2003, many methods have been proposed by researchers to simulate discharge for unobserved/ungauged catchments, such as, physical similarity, regression-based approaches, kriging, global average, inverse distance method (Kokkonen et al., 2003; McIntyre et al., 2005; Gitau & Chaubey, 2010; Samuel et al., 2011; Swain & Patra, 2017).

For use in hydrologic regionalization, a suitable hydrological model is to be adopted that can model the various hydrologic processes and help in water balance simulations. The Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) has been found to be convenient for comprehensive watershed analysis and management studies, and is a semi-distributed, continuous-time, and process-based model (Arnold et al., 1998; Krysanova & Srinivasan, 2014). Many researchers have used this model to simulate the runoff response of watersheds in different parts of the world with different land use/cover and varying climatic conditions (Hernandez et al., 2000; Conan et al., 2003; Liew & Garbrecht, 2003; Setegn et al., 2008; Murty et al., 2014; Du et al., 2018). Additionally, SWAT facilitates calibration using a semi-automated approach that can also perform sensitivity analysis and uncertainty assessment for use in hydrological modeling (Eawag 2009; van Griensven & Bauwens, 2003; Faramarzi et al., 2009; Arnold et al., 2012).

Numerous studies have investigated the importance of classifying watersheds into homogenous groups prior to regionalization to improve the predictions of streamflow in ungauged catchments. When the watersheds in a group are hydrologically similar, classification is said to be precise (Razavi & Coulibaly, 2013). These similar watersheds are quantified by selecting appropriate attributes or catchment characteristics. Various clustering algorithms, such as the K-means algorithm (Razavi & Coulibaly, 2013), hierarchical clustering (Farsadnia, 2015), Bayesian clustering (Sawicz et al., 2011), fuzzy clustering algorithm (Rao & Srinivas, 2006; Choubin et al., 2019) are used to group watersheds based on the selected attributes.

Incidentally, in the Subarnarekha-Brahmani-Baitarani River Basin region in Eastern India, nearly 30% of the watersheds are gauged, while for the remaining watersheds, we find that quantifying the streamflow data using regionalization techniques is the need of the hour. Considering the necessity of continuous streamflow data for the ungauged catchments, in this study, the combinations of different classification algorithms and methods for regionalization of hydrological model parameters are tested and compared, with application on a study watershed. The different methods adopted for the classification of hydrologically similar watersheds are Isomap (non-linear) and PCA (linear) dimensional reduction techniques, followed by K-means clustering. The watershed attributes needed for classification are extracted from physical factors and hydro-meteorological datasets and model parameters from the SWAT model after calibration of watersheds. The physical similarity (PS) and inverse distance weighting (IDW) regionalization methods on model parameters are then applied on the classified watersheds. In order to evaluate the performance of the different regionalization models, one of the gauged watersheds (Govindapur) is treated as an ungauged watershed, or a pseudo-ungauged watershed. The model parameters are then given as an input in SWAT to estimate the continuous streamflow for the pseudo-ungauged watershed.

2 Study Area and Data

The study area includes the watersheds of the Subarnarekha-Baitarani-Brahmani River Basin in India (Figure 1). The Subarnarekha River is one of the longest east-flowing inter-state rivers that drains into the Bay of Bengal. The Brahmani River is the second largest river in the State of Odisha. For the 12 selected watersheds of this region, the mean annual rainfall ranges from 1000 to 1800 mm. The temperature in the selected region is approximately 30°C during pre-monsoon season and falls up to 19°C during the winter season.

The current study utilized geographical and hydro-meteorological time-series datasets for hydrological modelling using SWAT. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) raster data with a spatial resolution of 30 m was used for the delineation of watersheds. Land use data for the study area at 1:250000 scale are obtained from the Bhuvan platform which is published under Bhuvan-Thematic Services of National Remote Sensing Centre of India. The land-use/land cover (LULC) maps are taken from the imagery available from multi-temporal satellite data of the IRS AWiFS sensor. The Indian Meteorological Department (IMD) provided gridded daily temperature data with a 0.5° spatial resolution and daily rainfall data with a 0.25° resolution for the period 1990-2020. The daily streamflow data recorded at gauging stations in the region required for hydrological model calibration and validation are obtained from the India-Water Resources Information System (WRIS) database.

Figure 1: Map of Subarnarekha-Brahmani-Baitarani River Basin region in Eastern India with the gauged and ungauged stream gauging station points

3 Methodology

In the present study, evaluation of state-of-the-art regionalization and classification techniques coupled with SWAT hydrological model is carried out to identify the most suitable approach

for regionalization of flows. The methods include linear (PCA) and non-linear (ISOMAP) dimensional reduction techniques on watershed attributes for classification (Table 1) which is followed by IDW and physical similarity regionalization methods. The watershed attributes are selected based on the availability of climatic and catchment characteristics. The dominant parameters are landuse type percentages, precipitation and temperature. Land use type vary significantly between the studied catchment area, with forest area ranging from 21% to 65% and agricultural area between 15% to 53% of the total area of the basin. Among all the study watersheds, Altuma is highly forested with 65% of area covered with forest followed by Champua with 55%. Nearly 47% and 40% of total area respectively are covered with agricultural land in Jambhira and Govindapur watersheds. The catchment area among the selected basins varies from 800 to 22000 sqkm, which after classification is found to have not much impact on the classification and regionalization methods. Mean annual rainfall (1990-2018) in the selected basins varies from 1100 mm to 1800 mm with Jambhira watershed getting the maximum mean annual rainfall of 1764 mm.

The performance evaluation of these techniques is carried out using Nash Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE) and coefficient of determination (R^2) values. The classification of hydrologically similar watersheds prior to regionalization helps in reduction of errors caused due to some dissimilar parameters or attributes.

3.1 Classification Methods

PCA is a method for detecting patterns in data and displaying them in such a way that their similarities and differences are highlighted by finding the linear combination between variables. Once the patterns have been discovered, the data can be compressed without much loss of information by reducing the dimensions. The first orthogonal principal component is the direction in which the majority of the variance in data is distributed, and the second orthogonal principle component is the direction in which the second-highest variance is distributed, and so on (Smith, 2002). The attributes with high weightage when projected on these principal components are extracted to group the watersheds using the K-means clustering technique.

Isomap is a non-linear dimensionality reduction technique that takes into account the geodesic distance rather than the Euclidean distance between the dataset keeping the non-linear data retained (Tenenbaum et al., 2000). The directions capturing most of the data variance are identified as the dominated dimensions or reduced dimensions. After the reduced dimensions are obtained, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient is estimated between the dimensions and the attributes to extract the influencing attributes. The attribute with higher value of Spearman's coefficient has contributed more to the respective dimension. The K-means clustering is then applied on the reduced attributes to group the watersheds.

3.2 Regionalization Methods

The inverse spatial distance between watershed centroids is used as the basis for Inverse Distance Weighting, an interpolation technique (Kanishka & Eldho, 2020; Swain & Patra, 2017). The IDW equation used in this study to estimate the model parameters is:

$$P_j = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i p_i \quad (1)$$

where n = number of gauged watersheds; p_i = model parameter of gauged watersheds, P_j = model parameter of an ungauged watershed and W_i = weight function of each gauged watershed

The parameters of the ungauged catchment are determined using the physical similarity approach by transferring the parameter values of the gauged basin that is most similar to the ungauged basin in terms of similarity index. Burn & Boorman (1993) provided the similarity index employed in this study as:

$$Dist_{t,d} = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|CD_{d,i} - CD_{t,i}|}{\Delta CD_i} \quad (2)$$

where, CD = catchment attributes, t = target catchment, d = donor catchments, n = number of catchment attributes, $\Delta CD_i = i^{\text{th}}$ catchment attribute range

Table 1: Watershed attributes selected for classification of watersheds

S. No.	Watershed Attribute
1	Catchment area (sqkm)
2	Mean slope (%)
3	Land-use percentage (2005-06, 2010-11 and 2015-16)
4	Maximum Elevation (m)
5	Longitude
6	Latitude
7	Mean annual precipitation (mm)
8	Mean pre-monsoon temperature (°C)
9	Mean monsoon temperature (°C)
10	Mean winter temperature (°C)
11	Mean post-monsoon temperature (°C)

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Classification of Homogeneous Watersheds

Firstly PCA is applied to the normalized watershed attributes of the 12 study watersheds in the study area to reduce the sensitivity due to the variable ranges. The first two PCs are found to account for more than 60% of the variance of attributes. Thus, the attributes are projected on these PCs, and the attributes with higher weightage are identified to group the watersheds using the K-means clustering technique. The reduced number of attributes are shown in Table 2, and then K-means clustering is performed. The grouping of watersheds into three groups (determined using the elbow method) based on the contributing attributes to PCs is shown in Figure 2.

The Isomap algorithm is then applied to the normalized watershed attributes, using the distance matrix among the watershed attributes. After the distances are determined, the neighbourhood points are estimated using the shortest distance with varying k nearest neighbour. Then, the

lower dimensions are identified and data are embedded on those dimensions. It is observed from Figure 3 that the first four dimensionally reduced components consist of more than 60% of the variance. To analyze the influencing attributes on the major dimensions, Spearman’s rank correlation coefficient is then estimated between the reduced dimensions and the attributes. Table 2 contains the contributing attributes to the different dimensions. Based on these, watershed classification into 3 different groups using K-means clustering is performed. The grouping of watersheds into three groups after k-means clustering is shown in Figure 2.

Table 2: List of influencing attributes used in PCA-based regionalization and with high spearman coefficient values

S.No	Attributes (PCA)	Attributes (Isomap)
1	Built up per05	Forest per 2005-06
2	Built up per10	Forest per 2010-11
3	Built up per15	Forest per 2015-16
4	Forest per05	Mean mon Temp
5	Forest per10	Mean post-mon Temp
6	Forest per15	Mean Annual pcp
7	Agri per15	Mean pre-mon Temp
8	Mean Annual pcp	Mean Slope per
9	Mean win T	Mean win Temp
10	Mean pre-mon T	Longitude
11	Mean mon T	Agri per 05
12	Mean post-mon T	

Figure 2: Clusters formed using PCA (left) and ISOMAP (right) techniques

Figure 3: Isomap variance plot indicating variance associated with different dimensions

4.2 SWAT Model Development

The calibration, validation, and sensitivity analysis of hydrological models of the 12 watersheds at a monthly time scale are performed in SWAT-CUP. The data was divided into calibration (1990-2010) and validation (2011-2018) datasets. During calibration, 300 simulations with three iterations are performed to identify the parameters sensitive to streamflow. The warm-up period is taken to be two years in each case. The parameters included in the calibration and regionalization exercise in the case of all the watersheds are kept the same (as shown in Table 3). The parameters selected for calibration and validation are based on previous research studies related to calibration of hydrological models and sensitivity analysis.

In the present study, the Govindapur watershed is taken as the pseudo-ungauged or target watershed, and the remaining gauged watersheds in the corresponding group as the donor watersheds. The performance of calibrated SWAT models developed for these donor catchments of Govindapur obtained from Isomap-based clustering (group# 3) and from PCA (group# 2) is summarized in Table 4. The R^2 values for donor watersheds under group 2 and group 3 are between 0.83 to 0.90, which are under the desired range. Also, NSE values of group 2 and 3 varied from 0.77 to 0.87. Thus, for all the watersheds, the model performance is satisfactory and under acceptable range as shown by the results of model calibration. Since it is assumed that Govindpur is the test watershed whose streamflow simulation would be performed using the regionalization, calibration has not been carried out for this watershed in the regionalization framework.

Table 3: Water balance parameters used for calibration of SWAT models and regionalization

S.No	Model parameters*	Description	Units
1	r_CN2	Initial SCS CN II value	
2	r_SOL_K	Saturated hydraulic conductivity	mm/h
3	r_SOL_AWC	Available water capacity of the soil layer	
4	r_GW_REVAP	Groundwater ‘revap’ coefficient	
5	a_ALPHA_BF	Baseflow recession factor	days
6	v_GW_DELAY	Groundwater delay	days
7	v_SLSUBBSN	Average slope length	m
8	r_ESCO	Soil evaporation compensation factors	
9	r_GWQMN	Threshold depth of water in the shallow aquifer required for return flow to occur	mm
10	v_OV_N	Manning’s ‘n’ value for overland flow	
11	a_SURLAG	Surface runoff lag coefficient	days
12	v_REVAPMN	Threshold depth for reevaporation to occur	mm

Note: *v means the existing parameter value is to be replaced by a given value; *a means the given value is added to the existing parameter value; *r means an existing parameter value is multiplied by (1+ the given value).

Table 4: Performance of SWAT models during calibration (1990-2010) period

S. No	Watershed	Group #	R ²	NSE
1	Tilga	2,3	0.90	0.83
2	Jarikela	2,3	0.83	0.82
3	Anandapur	3	0.86	0.84
4	Gomlai	2,3	0.89	0.87
5	Champua	2	0.86	0.77

4.3 Regionalization of Hydrological Parameters

The best model parameters are determined for the pseudo-ungauged watershed, and then manual calibration is performed in SWAT to obtain the daily streamflow records for the period 1992- 2010. The combination of different methods are compared based on R² and NSE values computed on monthly observed and simulated streamflows of the Govindapur watershed. The R² values of the entire data range for the calibration period are 0.80 when the PCA is combined with IDW, 0.73 when Isomap is combined with IDW, 0.73 with the physical similarity-based approach, and 0.54 when only K-means clustering is used without any dimensional reduction technique. The poor performance is observed while using K-means clustering classification method, which gets improved after employing dimensional reduction techniques prior to classification. Similarly, the NSE values are found to be 0.76 when the PCA is combined with

IDW, 0.72 when Isomap is combined with IDW, and 0.71 with the physical similarity-based approach.

Compared to other approaches, PCA with IDW is giving better results in the present study. It is also observed that IDW resulted in better performance in terms of regionalization as compared to the physical similarity method. While in the classification of similar watersheds, PCA has performed better than Isomap and K-means clustering algorithms. Thus, from the study, it is inferred that the combination of PCA with IDW is a better than other regionalization methods for this study area. However, adopting Isomap, the new non-linear technique, could also give considerably good results. The classification of watersheds prior to regionalization shows an improvement in flow estimation.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the comparison of different classification and regionalization methods are analyzed and reported for the Govindapur watershed of the Subarnarekha-Brahmani-Baitarani River Basin region. The watersheds are first classified into homogeneous clusters, followed by the IDW and physical similarity regionalization methods to obtain the SWAT model parameters for the ungauged watershed. Comparison of different classification methods for the selected attributes suggests that the combination of PCA with IDW performed better than other methods and is recommended for this region. Additionally, both the Isomap and PCA models could be therefore used for classification and regionalization. The classification techniques are also found to help in the removal of the errors in the transfer of some dissimilar parameters to the target (ungauged) watershed. Furthermore, including a larger number of watersheds in the study could improve the efficiency and reliability of the regionalization methodology. The choice of the suitable regionalization framework could further help water resources modelers to study water balance of the ungauged watersheds in the Subarnarekha-Brahmani-Baitarani River Basin region.

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